

News-based importance and sentiment about environmental issues: a composite index

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Introduction

Sentiment analysis applied to environmental news is a powerful tool for understanding public perception and engagement with critical ecological issues. By employing natural language processing techniques, sentiment analysis evaluates the relative importance of environmental topics in news articles as well as the tone of the discourse. In this paper we analyze alternative methods to construct an efficient measure of sentiment or attention; such an indicator may be intended to inform policymakers and environmental organizations (Luxon, 2019), but also useful as a signal to support financial operators in their market choices (Engle et al., 2020).

Methods

The methodology can be summarized as follows:

- 1) Articles appeared in several US journals are collected to build a huge amount of unstructured data.
- 2) We select a suitable list of keywords related to environmental issues and aggregate their importance in the text by constructing a composite index measure.
- 3) We test several aggregation approaches considering optimal weighting rules and we check whether one of them more than the others ensure accuracy and relevance of the composite measure.

As an example of application, we assess whether and to which extent alternative composite indicators affect major US market indexes.

Results

We believe that the introduction of a composite index to measure environmental attention (ECI) is highly beneficial and applications are

multifaceted. If well-constructed and robust, it provides a comprehensive assessment of the more representative discourses on the phenomenon from the newspapers point of view, thus allowing policymakers to identify strengths and weaknesses in environmental management. In addition, the composite index can serve as a leading indicator both in macroeconomic and financial analysis.

References

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